

VARIATION OF THE CATAPHORETIC VELOCITY OF SILVER HALIDES IN PRESENCE OF DIFFERENT DYESTUFFS.

By M. K. INDRA.

Measurements of cataphoretic velocities in presence of increasing concentrations of different dyestuffs have been made, which show that there is, in general, an increment of the c. v. valûes with increasing concentrations of the dye. There is also observed a time effect.

The theory of adsorption indicators as put forward by Fajans (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1931, 158, 107) or Kolthoff (*Chem Rev.*, 1935, 16, 87) has been shown to be not in good agreement with facts as observed by measurements of cataphoretic velocities under the exact conditions of titration (Chaudhury and Indra, to be published in the next issue of *this Journal*). Moreover these observations clearly indicate the specific nature of adsorption. In this paper measurements with increasing concentrations of dyestuffs have been made which clearly emphasize the specific nature of the adsorption of dyestuffs by silver halides.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Experiments were carried out with 1·8 c. c. of 0·1N-halide and 2 c. c. of 0·1N-silver nitrate with increasing amounts of the different acidic indicators. With methyl violet as indicator, 1. 8 c. c. of 0·1N-silver nitrate and 2 c. c. of 0·1N-KCl were taken. The results are given in Tables I—VI.

TABLE. I

Silver iodide and eosin.

0·1N-KI=1·8 c.c. 0·1N-AgNO ₃ =2 c.c. Total volume=100 c. c.			
Na-eosinate	Nature of the charge.	Time after mixing.	$V \times 10^5$.*
0·3 mg.	-ve	4-8 min.	14·0
		20-24	15·5
0·6	-ve	5-10	11·0
		15-19	15·24
		26-29	16·36
0·9	-ve	6-10	18·1
		16-19	21·1
1·2	-ve	5-7	20·83
		15-19	22·9

* V in Tables I—VI indicates velocity in cm./sec. per volt./cm.

TABLE II.

Silver iodide and fluorescein

0.1N-KI = 1.8 c. c. 0.1N-AgNO₃ = 2 c. c. Total volume = 100 c. c.

Fluoresceinate.	Nature of the charge.	Time after mixing.	V × 10 ⁵ .
0.15 mg.	+ve	5-9 min.	16.32
		15-19	20.85
		after 3 hrs.	15.48
0.3	-ve	5-10 min ₂	18.04
0.6	-ve	5-10	23.6
1.2	-ve	6-10	24.63
2.4	-ve	5-10	35.05

TABLE III.

Silver bromide and eosin

0.1N-KBr = 1.8 c. c. 0.1N-AgNO₃ = 2 c. c. Total volume = 100 c. c.

Na-eosinate	Nature of the charge	Time after mixing.	V × 10 ⁵ .
0.3 mg.	+ve	7-11 min ₁	19.68
		27-30	22.88
		36-40	23.2
		after 3 hrs ₂	...
0.6	-ve	5-10 min.	11.46
1.2	-ve	4-7	17.5
		12-16	18.26
1.8	-ve	5-9	29.9
		19-23	24.83

TABLE IV.

Silver bromide and fluorescein.

0.1N-KBr = 1.8 c.c. 0.1N-AgNO₃ = 2 c.c. Total volume = 100 c.c.

Fluoresceinate	Nature of the charge.	Time after mixing.	V × 10 ⁵ .
0.15 mg.	+ve	4-8 min.	17.6
	-ve	after 3 hours.	16.8
0.3	-ve	7-12 min.	19.9
		19-23	26.24
0.6	-ve	5-8	25.16
1.2	-ve	5-10	22.27
2.4	-ve	5-10	24.55
		16-20	27.75

TABLE V.

Silver chloride and fluorescein.

0.1N-KCl = 1.8 c.c. 0.1N-AgNO₃ = 2 c.c. Total volume = 100 c.c.

Na-fluoresceinate.	Nature of the charge.	Time after mixing.	V × 10 ⁵ .
0.15 mg.	-ve	5-10 min.	11.47
0.3	-ve	4-8	14.96
0.6	-ve	5-10	17.5
1.2	-ve	5-10	20.83

TABLE VI.

Silver chloride and methyl violet.

0.1N-KCl = 2 c.c. 0.1N-AgNO₃ = 1.8 c.c. Total volume = 100 c.c.

Na-salt of methyl violet-	Nature of the charge.	Time after mixing.	V × 10 ⁵ .
0.15 mg.	-ve	4-8 min.	12.68
		15-18	19.4
	+ve	after 3 hrs.	16.57
0.6	+ve	4-8 min.	17.3
		15-20	24.08
1.2	+ve	4-8	25.48
2.4	+ve	6-12	24.43

D I S C U S S I O N.

It would be found from the experimental results that there is in general an increase in the c.v. values of the silver halides with increasing amounts of the indicator ion. When an acidic indicator is used, the charge of the silver halide has been kept always positive (silver ion in excess 0.1N-KH = 1.8 c.c. and 0.1N-AgNO₃ = 2 c.c.), while with a basic indicator the charge of the silver halide used is negative (chlorine ion in excess 0.1N-KCl = 2 c.c. 0.1N-AgNO₃ = 1.8 c. c.). There is to be observed also a time effect.

Considerations of the experimental results with any one single indicator with a particular halide, appear to support the views of the secondary electrical adsorption of the dye. But when we consider the effects observed with a single adsorbent and different indicators, specific nature of adsorption is at once marked. Two types of equilibrium are to be kept in view in explaining the variation of the cataphoretic velocities of silver halides with increasing concentrations of dyestuffs, for when silver nitrate and potassium halides are mixed, the colloidal precipitate that forms takes time to come to equilibrium and to attain its final growth. So the adsorption reaction that takes place between the silver halide and the dyestuff ion is somewhat modified by the velocity of the growth of the particles to its final size, though after some time, the latter effect is practically nil (*cf.* Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Bhabak, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 370; Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Sen-Gupta, *ibid.*, 1936, **13**, 421).

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PHYSICO-CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA.

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